

Transforming Early Childhood Education (The Impact of Decree of The Minister of Education, Culture, Research and Technology No 56/2022 at Kindergarten Cilacap Indonesia)

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ABSTRACT

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The aims to study is describe the implementation of the independence curriculum at Aisyiyah BA Cimanggu Cilacap Kindergarten, which is guided by Ministry of Education and Culture Number 56 of 2022. This research uses a qualitative approach with the type of education policy study it involves. The results of the study show that the implementation of Ministry of Education and Culture Number 56 of 2022 at Aisyiyah BA Cimanggu Cilacap Kindergarten is carried out through three activities: first, lesson planning. In this activity, you will: (1) formulate goals; (2) choose the learning experiences that students want to receive; (3) determine teaching and learning activities; (4) determine the people involved in the learning process; (5) determine the tools and materials for learning; (6) pay attention to the availability of physical facilities; and (7) plan the evaluation and development process. Second is the implementation of learning. In this activity, it is carried out by (1) conveying the goals and motivation of students; (2) presenting information; (3) organizing students into study groups; (4) guiding work and study groups; (5) evaluating; and (6) giving awards. Third, learning assessment In the assessment process, activities are carried out to: (1) determine research plans and objectives; (2) determine the appropriate assessment technique; (3) carry out the assessment process; (4) analyze the assessment; and (5) adapt learning.

KEYWORDS:

leadership, characteristics, Islamic educational institutions

INTRODUCTION

The Indonesian government periodically endeavors to enhance the caliber of its human capital, with education being one of its main tools. Human resources capable of competing and rising to the challenges of the twenty-first century will be generated via high-quality education.¹ The curriculum is still a hot topic of discussion. Curriculum changes provide a new paradigm for the field of education, including providing freedom to teachers in controlling the learning process and providing student agency, where rights

and obligations are obtained by students in learning. Then through the independent curriculum the learning process becomes homogenized at all levels of education.² The independent curriculum is no longer used as a discourse in the field of education. The national curriculum's primary features are its links to community needs and national goals, its flexibility to allow for local adaptation, and its standardization to guarantee equitable and high-quality education.³

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¹ Siswadi, Asri Fuadi, and Abu Dharin, "Development of Learning Cycle-Based Science Learning Devices to Improve Elementary School Students' Creative Thinking Ability," *Jurnal Penelitian Pendidikan IPA* 9, no. No. 4 (2023).

² Yogi Anggraena et al., "Kajian Akademik: Kurikulum Untuk Pemulihan Pembelajaran," *Pusat Kurikulum Dan Pembelajaran Badan Standar, Kurikulum, Dan Asesmen Pendidikan Kebudayaan Riset Dan Teknologi*, 2021.

³ Muh. Hanif et al., "Pesantren Resistance To Indonesia's National Curriculum To Defend Its Curriculum

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Currently, several levels of education are starting to implement an independent curriculum. This is because only through an independent curriculum, teachers and students are freed in the learning process. For example, teachers are free to choose teaching methods, teaching materials, learning media, and so on. Quoted from the results of the author's observation with the head of Aisyiyah BA Cimanggu Kindergarten.⁴ The implementation of the independent curriculum still experiences various problems, especially with stakeholders such as teachers who do not understand the independent curriculum, lack of expertise, and lack of participation in the socialization of the independent curriculum. At the kindergarten level, these problems have an impact on the unpreparedness of schools to implement curriculum changes. This can be seen from the lack of readiness of SMEs, facilities and infrastructure that have not supported, and so on.

As we know that the independent curriculum is based on the opinion of Nadiem Makarim as the Minister of Education and Culture that independent learning is defined as freedom of thought. The definition of the concept of independent learning in early childhood can be summarized as 'freedom to play' and is considered different from the next level of education. The concept of freedom to play in children is in accordance with the characteristics of children, where early childhood is more active in playing and without any demands to learn.⁵ In addition, the Curriculum also focuses on shaping the child's personality.⁶ Currently, Indonesia is experiencing considerable problems, especially in the field of education, namely the low level of literacy of Indonesian society. This is reinforced by the survey results obtained from the Program for International Student Assessment (PISA) in 2019, that Indonesia ranks 62nd out of 70 countries in terms of literacy.⁷ The implementation of an independent curriculum in the education sector is a wise solution from the government to restore the education sector.

Another reason that supports the implementation of independent learning is that the learning process has been left behind (learning lost) as a result of the co-19 pandemic. Children are no longer enthusiastic about learning and the learning process is no longer fun. Whereas learning at school should be fun. This statement is in accordance with the theory introduced by Jean Piaget, that learning is a learning process that does not expect value.⁸ The independent learning curriculum in kindergarten is very interesting to study. This is because early childhood is in the golden age period, where brain development takes place optimally if given the right stimuli. Therefore, the independent learning curriculum focuses on exploring children's potential naturally.⁹ The learning process using the independent learning curriculum provides freedom for children to play according to the themes provided by the teacher. In other words, learning at the PAUD level practices learning by doing, where learning is more often practical (outdoor) and applies a kinesthetic learning style.¹⁰ The independent curriculum also requires children to think critically about things. In accordance with the output to be achieved, students can explore their own potential, so that they can foster a sense of independence. This process begins with meeting the needs of students. Therefore, the independent curriculum is seen as suitable for children to become more independent.¹¹ In addition, the reason that makes the author interested in studying the independent learning curriculum in early childhood is that there is still little discussion about the independent curriculum. This is because at the PAUD level, the new independent curriculum is allowed to be implemented in July 2022. The majority of kindergartens (TK) are not yet ready to implement the independent learning curriculum. Reporting from the Kemendikbud news page, Anindito as the Head of the Agency, Curriculum, and Assessment of the Ministry of Education and Culture said that the implementation of the independent curriculum will still be enforced on July 12, 2022.¹²

Model," *RGSA – Revista de Gestão Social e Ambiental* 18, no. No. 7 (n.d.): 1–32.

⁴ "Hasil Wawancara Dengan Kepala Sekolah TK Aisyiyah BA Cimanggu Yakni Ibu Alfatihah S.Pd. AUD., M.Pd Pada Tanggal 15 Juli 2022, Pukul 11.56," n.d.

⁵ Yosep Kurniawan, "Implementasi Merdeka Belajar Berdasarkan Ajaran Tamansiswa Dalam Pembelajaran Bahasa Inggris Lembaga Kursus Kelas Anak-Anak" (Yogyakarta: Pascasarjana Pendidikan, 2020), hlm. 104.

⁶ Alyse C Hachey, Song A An, and Diane E Golding, "Nurturing Kindergarteners' Early STEM Academic Identity Through Makerspace Pedagogy," *Early Childhood Education Journal* 50 (2022).

⁷ Admin, "Tingkat Literasi Indonesia Di Dunia Rendah, Ranking 62 Dari 70 Negara," Perpustakaan Kemendagri, 2021, <https://perpustakaan.kemendagri.go.id/tingkat-literasi-indonesia-di-dunia-rendah-ranking-62-dari-70-negara/>.

⁸ Titania Widya Prameswari, "Merdeka Belajar : Sebuah Konsep Pembelajaran Anak Usia Dini Menuju Indonesia Emas 2045," vol. 1 (Kediri, 2020), hlm. 79.

⁹ Abu Dharin, "Pengembangan Kreativitas Siswa Dalam Pembelajaran Di Mi Ma'arif NU 01 Pageraji Kecamatan Cilongok Kabupaten Banyumas," *JPA* 16, no. No. 1 (2015).

¹⁰ Siska Maria and Wuri Astuti, "Gaya Belajar Kinestetik Anak TK Muslimat NU 9 Ahmad Yani," *Jurnal Pendidikan Anak Usia Dini* 2, no. 2 (2020): hlm. 63.

¹¹ Nanda Alfian Kurniawan et al., "Urgensi Pendidikan Berpikir Kritis Era Merdeka Belajar Bagi Peserta Didik," *Tarbawi: Jurnal Ilmu Pendidikan* 16, no. 1 (2020): hlm. 107.

¹² PaudPedia, "Implementasi Kurikulum Merdeka Diseluruh Jenjang Pendidikan PAUD Dasar Dan Menengah Tetap Dilaksanakan Tidak Ada Pembatalan," *Audpedia.Kemendikbud*, 2022, <https://paudpedia.kemendikbud.go.id/berita/implementasi->

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The discussion of research findings is indeed the culmination of journal writing, so first the author presents the work of other researchers related to the author's work. In addition, other authors' works can be used as reference material by using the same discussion, namely the independent learning curriculum, including: First, the results of Kasmawati's research with the title "Teacher Perceptions in the Concept of Education (Study on the Implementation of Independent Learning at SMAN 5 Takalar)".¹³ The implementation of an independent curriculum at SMAN 5 Takalar has a positive impact on teachers, namely teachers are given freedom in delivering material, so that their creativity increases. But the independent learning curriculum is hampered due to the lack of knowledge possessed by stakeholders; Second, the results of Atika Widyastuti's research with the title "Teacher Perceptions of the Concept of Independent Learning of Minister of Education and Culture Nadiem Makarim in Islamic Religious Education at MTs Negeri 3 Sleman."¹⁴ The independent learning curriculum implemented at MTs Negeri 3 Sleman provides positive perceptions for teachers, including teachers willing to follow existing policies, making lesson plans runs effectively and without obstacles, and implementing learning that is already interactive and communicative; Third, the results of Belinda Galuh Pramudya Wardani's research with the title "Implementation of the Independent Learning Curriculum Policy and Independent Campus in the Perspective of Constructivism Theory at Muhammadiyah University Malang."¹⁵ At the tertiary level, to be precise at Muhammadiyah University of Malang, the independent learning curriculum has been implemented to the fullest, even the exchange of learning in each study program has been carried out.

Based on other references, what distinguishes the independent curriculum from the author's work is that it focuses on the kindergarten level and discusses learning starting from learning planning, learning implementation, and learning assessment in the independent curriculum. This research needs to be done because there is no work that discusses the same thing as what the author wants to study.

This study aims to describe the implementation of an independent curriculum at Aisyiyah BA Cimanggu Kindergarten which is guided by the Ministry of Education and Culture Number 56 of 2022, so that a formulation of the problem that the author wants to discuss is the

implementation of the Ministry of Education and Culture Number 56 of 2022 at Aisyiyah BA Cimanggu Kindergarten Cilacap? In order to make it easier for the author to answer the problem studied, a derivative formulation is made, including: (1) learning planning in the implementation of Ministry of Education and Research Number 56 of 2022 in Aisyiyah BA Cimanggu Cilacap Kindergarten; (2) learning implementation in the implementation of Ministry of Education and Research Number 56 of 2022 in Aisyiyah BA Cimanggu Cilacap Kindergarten; (3) learning assessment in the implementation of Ministry of Education and Research Number 56 of 2022 in Aisyiyah BA Cimanggu Cilacap Kindergarten.

RESEARCH METHODS

The author uses a qualitative approach with a policy study model. In the policy study model, the author compares the thing under study, namely the implementation of the independent learning curriculum at Aisyiyah BA Cimanggu Cilacap Kindergarten with the independent learning curriculum guidelines. The measuring tool in this research is the Ministry of Education and Culture Number 56 of 2022. This research was conducted at Aisyiyah BA Cimanggu Cilacap Kindergarten, which is located on Jalan Masjid, Cimanggu, Cimanggu District, Cilacap Regency, Central Java Province. This research was conducted in November-December 2022. The subjects in this study were the principal and kindergarten teachers as resource persons who support sources of information, as well as students who can be used as observation material regarding child development when implementing the independent learning curriculum. While the object of research is the independent learning curriculum at Aisyiyah BA Cimanggu Kindergarten Cilacap. The data obtained by the author comes from the Mills & Huberman analysis technique with the help of collecting information through interviews, observation, and documentation activities. In order for research activities to be structured, the author uses research instruments with three sub-points of discussion, namely learning planning, learning implementation, and learning assessment. From these three sub-points, the author obtained indicators related to the research, so that the information obtained became more detailed. Meanwhile, to test the validity of the data, the author applied source triangulation as a data validity test. Data checking began by conducting interviews with the Head of

kurikulum-merdeka-diseluruh-jenjang-pendidikan-paud-dasar-dan-menengah-tetap-dilaksanakan-tidak-ada-pembatalan?id=1023&ix=11.

¹³ Kasmawati, "Persepsi Guru Dalam Konsep Pendidikan (Studi Pada Penerapan Merdeka Belajar Di SMA Negeri 5 Takalar)" (Universitas Muhammadiyah Makassar, 2021).

¹⁴ Atika Widyastuti, "Persepsi Guru Tentang Konsep Merdeka Belajar Mendikbud Nadiem Makarim Dalam

Pendidikan Agama Islam Di MTs Negeri 3 Sleman" (UII, 2020).

¹⁵ Belinda Galuh Pramudya Wardani, "Implementasi Kebijakan Kurikulum Merdeka Belajar Dan Kampus Merdeka Dalam Perspektif Teori Konstruktivisme Di Universitas Muhammadiyah Malang" (Universitas Muhammadiyah Malang, 2022).

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Aisyiyah BA Cimanggu Cilacap Kindergarten, then continued by conducting interviews with several other sources, namely class A teachers and class B teachers at Aisyiyah BA Cimanggu Cilacap Kindergarten. To find out more information, researchers rechecked the results of interviews with the results of observations that researchers made during the research period to find out how the implementation of the Ministry of Education and Culture No. 56 of 2022 in Aisyiyah BA Cimanggu Cilacap Kindergarten.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Permendikbud Number 56 of 2022 is a guideline in implementing the independent learning curriculum. Researchers relate the research results to the guidelines to obtain a conclusion regarding the success or failure of the implementation of the independent curriculum implemented by Aisyiyah BA Cimanggu Kindergarten. The results on the implementation of the independent curriculum at Aisyiyah BA Cimanggu Kindergarten are in accordance with the guidelines. This can be seen from the indicators in the implementation of the independent learning curriculum.

1. PAUD learning planning is based on Ministry of Education and Research Number 56 of 2022. In learning planning activities, the steps taken include:

First, formulate objectives. The specific objectives of the independent curriculum are designed by looking at the needs of the community. Looking at the existing conditions, Kindergarten Aisyiyah BA Cimanggu Cilacap is located in a middle to lower economic community, so the planned curriculum is adjusted to the background of the surrounding conditions. The following are the specific objectives of Aisyiyah BA Cimanggu Kindergarten, including: strengthening meaningful play activities as a learning process, strengthening the relevance of PAUD as the initial foundation phase, strengthening the love of literacy and numeracy from an early age, the project of strengthening the Pancasila profile in accordance with the independent learning curriculum, strengthening the role of parents as unit partners. Specific objectives are made according to the needs of the community. According to the head of kindergarten (2022), before making special goals, the head of kindergarten needs to observe the environment around the kindergarten, so that the goals made are in accordance with the needs of the community. As a result, teachers are freed to plan learning both from learning methods, learning media, and so on.

In accordance with the opinion of class A and B teachers (2022), that learning topics are tailored to the needs and characters of students, so that learning becomes more enjoyable. Although the specific objectives have been formulated well, in the field there are two obstacles in learning, namely first, obstacles that come from students. This obstacle can occur when the teacher has prepared learning materials and media, but many students do not leave due to illness or other reasons. Therefore, the teacher must repeat the learning material at that time on another day. Meanwhile, obstacles originating from teachers can occur when teachers have many activities such as teacher meetings with their organizations that aim to improve teacher competence. Then to get feedback from the community regarding specific objectives, the kindergarten head has the right strategy, namely by informing the public about the independent learning curriculum and various programs that have been designed by Aisyiyah BA Cimanggu Kindergarten Cilacap.

Education should be able to keep up with the times, therefore the goals of education must be balanced, so that not only become someone who is knowledgeable but students can become good citizens.¹⁶ According to Soekmadinata in Principles in Curriculum Development that to formulate educational objectives based on various sources, such as government regulations and policies, surveys of public perceptions of needs, surveys of the views of experts, and so on.¹⁷ In the learning process, researchers observed that the specific objectives of the curriculum had been carried out well. This is evidenced by the fact that in class A, students are given the freedom to choose what they like. Teachers also teach various good habits such as praying before and after eating, teaching independence by learning without being waited for by the learner's guardian, and so on. Adults have a duty to actively support children's learning in the guided-learning domain of socialization.¹⁸ The value of independence needs to be taught from an early age, because it can affect the future of students when they are adults. According to Novan Ardy Wiyani, revealed that there are three reasons that make character education very important to be implemented early, including: first, students are individuals who are considered unable to know good and bad behavior; second, students cannot distinguish between good and bad behavior; third, students do not understand the impact of good and bad behavior.¹⁹

¹⁶ Muhammad Kristiawan, *Analisis Pengembangan Kurikulum Dan Pembelajaran* (Bengkulu: Unit Penerbitan dan Publikasi FKIP Universitas Bengkulu, 2019).

¹⁷ Arif Rahman Prasetyo and Tasman Hamami, "Prinsip-Prinsip Dalam Pengembangan Kurikulum," *PALAPA: Jurnal Studi Keislaman Dan Ilmu Pendidikan* 2 8, no. 1 (2020): hlm. 53.

¹⁸ Laurence Labelle, "Associations between Socioeconomic Status, Child Risk Factors, and Parenting during Guided Learning," *Journal of Applied Developmental Psychology* 91 (2024).

¹⁹ Novan Ardy Wiyani, "Perencanaan Strategik Pembentukan Karakter Anak Usia Dini Di TK Islam Al-

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Secondly, choosing the learning experience that students want to receive. Learning experiences can determine how a person will behave in the future. This is in accordance with Basleman and Mappa, that learning is the result of a person's interaction with the environment, so that it can be said to be a process of changing potential appearance.²⁰ Through social interactions, children pick up language. Individual differences in children's language proficiency at school entry are largely caused by variations in the quantity and quality of language interactions children engage in during the preschool years.²¹

Knowing the importance of learning experiences in early childhood, learning experiences must be carefully sorted out. From the results of interviews with the head of kindergarten, learning has taken place with various media, not only visual. Meanwhile, according to class A and B teachers, learning becomes meaningful because teachers have utilized play dough in class A, while in class B teachers have started using provocation sentences so that children are more creative. The kindergarten principal also implemented strategies to ensure that learning is in line with the curriculum. This is done through the creation of a semester. In addition, the role of learning media also plays a role in the success of planning. In learning media, teachers have started using creative and innovative learning, namely recycled media (loose parts).²²

Third, determining teaching and learning activities. Teaching and learning activities can be said to be successful if learning can provide positive changes to students, including making students a critical person and can develop their potential.²³ Learning methods also affect the success of learning. Therefore, teachers must plan learning using methods that are as interesting as

possible. According to the Head of Kindergarten, children are very difficult to concentrate for a long duration, so the selection of learning methods is very important. Children's collaborative play is determined by the duration they get.²⁴ Teachers need to mix and match methods so that children will not be bored in learning, for example when teachers only use one method, it is certain that children will be bored and not interested in learning.²⁵ Kindergarten has implemented a differentiated curriculum, where learning is required to be creative and innovative. Every theme peak is carried out an interesting activity, for example the peak of the Farmer-Ku theme, then the kindergarten carries out MarketDay. The involvement of all stakeholders determines the success of learning.

Fourth, determine the people involved in the learning process. At the kindergarten level, learning is often called play. As a partner of children, the teacher has the obligation to direct and transfer all of his knowledge to children. To maximize their role as partners, teachers need to master four competencies in accordance with Government Regulation No. 19 of 2005 concerning National Standards for Education and Education Personnel.²⁶ Learning can also be interpreted as a collaborative process between teachers and students.²⁷ Therefore, the Head of Kindergarten also helps prepare teaching materials when the teacher has a sudden interest. Active learning has several characteristics, one of which is learner-centered.²⁸ Aisyiyah Kindergarten has implemented active learning through various learning media that are interesting for children such as using stories, loose parts, play collaboration, and so on.

Fifth, determine the tools and materials for learning. Tools and materials in learning can be said to be

Irsyad Purwokerto," *Al-Athfal: Jurnal Pendidikan Anak* 3, no. 2 (2017): hlm. 111.

²⁰ Bagus Kisworo, "Implementasi Media Pembelajaran Berbasis Prinsip-Prinsip Pendidikan Orang Dewasa Di Pkbn Indonesia Pusaka Ngaliyan Semarang," *Journal of Nonformal Education* 3, no. 1 (2017): hlm. 84.

²¹ Erika Hoff et al., "Context and Education Affect the Quality of Parents' Speech to Children," *Journal of Applied Developmental Psychology* 91 (March 2024): 101632, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.appdev.2024.101632>.

²² Dwi Priyanto and Abu Dharin, "Students Creativity Development Model and Its Implementation in Indonesian Islamic Elementary School," *Pegem Journal of Education and Instruction* 11, no. No. 3 (2021): 81–87.

²³ Zuriatun Hasanah, "Model Pembelajaran Kooperatif Dalam Menumbuhkan Keaktifan Belajar Siswa," *IRSYADUNA: Jurnal Studi Kemahasiswaan* 1, no. 1 (2021): hlm. 11.

²⁴ Anita Bundy et al., "Sydney Playground Project: A Cluster-Randomized Trial to Increase Physical Activity, Play, and Social Skills," *Journal of School Health* 87, no. 10 (2017).

²⁵ Novan Ardy Wiyani and Nurkamelia Mukhtar AH, "Pembentukan Karakter Pada Anak Usia Dini Melalui Program Toilet Training," *Kindergarten: Journal of Islamic Early Childhood Education* 5, no. 1 (2022): hlm. 108.

²⁶ Anastasia Weti, "Upaya Meningkatkan Kemampuan Guru Menyusun Rencana Pelaksanaan Pembelajaran Harian (RPPH) Melalui Teknik Latihan Dan Bimbingan Pada Guru TK/PAUD Gugus I Kecamatan Wolomeze Tahun Pelajaran 2017/2019," *Ejurnal Imedtech* 2, no. 2 (2018): hlm. 12.

²⁷ Isnawardatul Bararah, "Efektifitas Perencanaan Pembelajaran Dalam Pembelajaran Pendidikan Agama Islam Di Sekolah," *Jurnal Mudarrisuna* 7, no. 1 (2017): hlm. 139.

²⁸ Hari Rohayati, "Penerapan Pembelajaran Kooperatif Model Group Investigation Untuk Meningkatkan Aktivitas Dan Hasil Belajar Siswa Kelas VII-1 Pada Materi Pokok Segi Empat SMPN 3 Mataram Tahun Pelajaran 2017/2018," *FJAS: Famosa Journal of Applied Sciences* 1, no. 4 (2022): hlm. 550, <https://doi.org/10.55927/fjas.v1i4.1329>.

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learning media that support smooth learning. In the independent learning curriculum, learning can use simple media and recycled products (loost parts). The more creative the teacher, the more interesting the learning media will be for students to learn. The curiosity and interest of learners is the first step to successful learning. According to the Head of Kindergarten, the tools and materials in learning are well-supplied. The uniqueness of the learning method also determines children's interest in learning. According to class A and B teachers, the use of tools and materials must be adjusted to the learning topic. Both use different tools and materials. Learning using the learning independence curriculum is more focused on recovery learning methods or what can be called methods that focus on direct learning.²⁹ For example, in learning about trees, the teacher will introduce all parts of the tree and bring them directly during learning. The use of different learning methods for students can certainly affect the development of students.³⁰

Sixth, pay attention to the availability of physical facilities. Physical facilities in early childhood, namely various types of games used by students to play at Aisyiyah BA Cimanggu Kindergarten Cilacap. The Head of Kindergarten expressed his opinion that in kindergarten for play facilities is still insufficient, but the limitations can be overcome by providing play duration in each class. Play media is also included in learning facilities because it supports the effectiveness of learning.³¹ In addition, play is also influenced by the nature of the environment and the availability of resources.³² Play media for children can affect children's behavior.³³ Another theory explains that play can also increase mindfulness in children so that children become happy and cheerful.³⁴

Seventh, planning the evaluation and development process. According to the principal, the evaluation carried out at Aisyiyah BA Cimanggu Kindergarten in Cilacap has implemented a scientific approach and teachers have used anecdotal records to describe the development of students. In addition, in classes A and B the evaluation

process is very different. In class A, teachers carry out observations on the habits that have been taught by the teacher. While in class B, the evaluation is done through a photo series. In accordance with Permendikbud No. 65 on Assessment Standards and Permendikbud No. 81 on curriculum implementation, this includes evaluation procedures, learning evaluation instruments, and evaluation implementation guidelines.³⁵ According to the head of the kindergarten, the teaching carried out in the kindergarten has illustrated the achievements that are proven by monitoring the development of students well.

2. The implementation of PAUD learning is based on the Ministry of Education and Research No. 56 of 2022. In carrying out the implementation of learning, the following steps are taken:

First, conveying objectives and motivating learners. The purpose of the learning topic needs to be conveyed by the teacher before entering the lesson. Teachers also need to motivate students to be enthusiastic in learning. As a leader, the kindergarten principal also motivates teachers by reminding them that teachers are the spearhead of learning, so whether or not students understand learning depends on how the teacher delivers. The motivation given can be through the provision of intensive. Meanwhile, motivation for students can be through giving praise, appreciation in the form of snacks, and so on. Motivation can also be conveyed by reminding students of tomorrow's learning material so as to create enthusiasm in learning

Second, it provides information. Information can be achieved by interaction between two or more parties through communication. According to the Head of Kindergarten, the teacher's ability to communicate is very important because it can determine the understanding of students. Meanwhile, according to Novan Ardy Wiyani, to introduce good behavior, teachers need to give examples first so that children understand good and bad behavior. Then the learning method is quite influential in

²⁹ Ahdar Djameluddin and Wardana, *Belajar Dan Pembelajaran: 4 Pilar Peningkatan Kompetensi Pedagogis* (Parepare: CV. Kaaffah Learning Center, 2019).

³⁰ Natalie Robertson, Anne-Marie Morrissey, and Deborah Moore, "From Boats to Bushes: Environmental Elements Supportive of Children's Sociodramatic Play outdoors," *Children's Geographies* 18, no. 2 (2020).

³¹ Citra Angraini and Nani Imaniyati, "Fasilitas Belajar Dan Manajemen Kelas Sebagai Determinan Terhadap Prestasi Belajar Siswa," *Jurnal Pendidikan Manajemen Perkantoran* 3, no. 2 (2018): hlm. 207, <https://doi.org/10.17509/jpm.v3i2.11766>.

³² Anne-Marie Morrissey, Caroline Scott Rahimi, and Mark, "A Comparison of Sociodramatic Play Processes of Preschoolers in a Naturalized and a Traditional outdoor Space," *International Journal of Play* 6, no. 2 (2017).

³³ Lina Engelen et al., "Spying on Children during a School Playground Intervention Using a Novel Method for Direct observation of Activities during Outdoor Play," *Journal of Adventure Education and Outdoor Learning* 8, no. 1 (2018).

³⁴ Regina Lai Tong Lee et al., "Effects of an Unstructured Free Play and Mindfulness Intervention on Wellbeing in Kindergarten Students," *International Journal of Environmental and Public Health* 17, no. 15 (2017).

³⁵ Sugiyanto, Badrun Kartowagiran, and Jailani, "Pengembangan Model Evaluasi Proses Pembelajaran Matematika Di SMP Berdasarkan Kurikulum 2013," *Jurnal Penelitian Dan Evaluasi Pendidikan* 19, no. 1 (2015): hlm. 85.

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conveying information to students which can be applied through learning methods.³⁶

Third, organizing students into learning groups. One way to build character at an early age is through learning groups. Learners will get used to working with others, combining the ideas they get, and working together on what they want. The value obtained in learning groups is the value of independence and collaboration. Another opinion reveals that future challenges require students to learn the value of independence.³⁷ The group learning model has four activities, namely introductory activities, core activities, breaks/meals, and closing. This model is defined as learning where students are divided into several groups but with different activities.³⁸ Based on the results of interviews with the principal, it can be seen that learning can run optimally if the Head of Kindergarten participates in supervising the course of learning. So the Head of Kindergarten always observes and analyzes learning, then provides input and suggestions for learning that has taken place. Learning in kindergarten has implemented the cooperative learning method through various projects given to students.³⁹

Fourth, guiding group work and learning. The enthusiasm of students in learning both individually and in groups determines the success of learning. Based on the interview with the principal, it can be seen that teacher communication is directly proportional to the enthusiasm of students. If the teacher starts the learning with cheerfulness, of course the feedback given by students will be good, for example by being active during the learning process. Two-way communication can be assessed as weighty if the teacher reads a lot of literacy. The teacher as the direction giver in cooperative learning should have a strategy so that students can cooperate with their peers. Based on the results of the interview with the

class A teacher, it can be seen that the project grouping is adjusted to the children's interest in something. For example, in the project of making vehicles, children are given the freedom to choose their tasks such as making wheels, glass, and so on, so that they can foster togetherness and cooperation between children. Through habituation, children can get used to working on cooperation projects. The habituation method can be used to educate students. This is because through this method, students can be optimized to the maximum of their development.⁴⁰ The impact is that students will get used to doing things that are used as habituation and can be applied in everyday life. The best results can be obtained if the teacher is always involved in habituation and of course disciplines habituation activities continuously.⁴¹

Fifth, evaluation. Based on the results of interviews with the Head of Kindergarten, it can be seen that to support the learning process and evaluation. In Aisyiyah BA Cimanggu Kindergarten Cilacap, the Head of Kindergarten also helps prepare teaching materials when teachers encounter obstacles, so that the learning process can take place optimally. Early childhood development is not based on grades, but on the process it goes through. The results of evaluation on students can be used as a reflection for further learning.⁴²

Sixth, giving awards. Reward or commonly called an award is an appreciation given to someone for the good things they do. The form of reward is divided into two, namely first, verbal. second, non-verbal.⁴³ M. Ngalm Purwanto argues that rewards are equipment in educating children so that children are happy because their actions are rewarded.⁴⁴ For early childhood, giving rewards in the form of praise alone can give happiness to students. The impact is that children are more enthusiastic about learning. Rewards will be obtained if students have the

³⁶ Novan Ardy Wiyani, "Epistemologi Pendidikan Anak Bagi Ayah Menurut Luqman," *Yinyang: Jurnal Studi Islam, Gender Dan Anak* 14, no. 2 (2019): hlm. 318, <https://doi.org/10.24090/yinyang.v14i2.2019.pp>.

³⁷ Novan Ardy Wiyani, "Manajemen Perilaku Ketidakmandirian Sosial-Emosi Pada Anak Usia Dini Di TK Aisyiyah XIV Kedung Wuluh Purwokerto," *ThufuLA: Jurnal Inovasi Pendidikan Guru Raudhatul Athfal* 6, no. 1 (2018): hlm. 23.

³⁸ Novan Ardy Wiyani, "Manajemen Program Kegiatan PAUD Berbasis Otak Kanan," *Awlady: Jurnal Pendidikan Anak* 4, no. 1 (2018): hlm. 105.

³⁹ Syarif Hisyam Addailami and Agus Budi Santoso, "Pengaruh Model Pembelajaran Kooperatif Tipe Talking Stick Pada Mata Pelajaran Teknik Listrik Terhadap Hasil Belajar Siswa Kelas X TAV Di SMK Negeri 2 Surabaya," *Jurnal Pendidikan Elektro* 6, no. 3 (2017): hlm. 302.

⁴⁰ Novan Ardy Wiyani, "Pengembangan Program Kegiatan Pembiasaan Berbasis TQM Di Raudhatul Athfal

(RA)," *Awlady: Jurnal Pendidikan Anak* 3, no. 1 (2017): hlm. 4.

⁴¹ Novan Ardy Wiyani, "Optimalisasi Kecerdasan Spiritual Bagi Anak Usia Dini Menurut Abdullah Nashih Ulwan," *ThufuLA: Jurnal Inovasi Pendidikan Guru Raudhatul Athfal* 4, no. 2 (2016): hlm. 94.

⁴² Adelia Miranti Sidiq, "Pengembangan Kreativitas Anak Melalui Konsep Merdeka Belajar Di Sanggar Anak Alam," *Seling: Jurnal Program Studi PGRA* 6, no. 2 (2020): hlm. 148.

⁴³ Ina Magdalena et al., "Metode Pembelajaran Pemberian Reward Terhadap Siswa Kelas 5 SD Bubulak 2 Kota Tangerang," *EDISI: Jurnal Edukasi Dan Sains* 2, no. 1 (2020): hlm. 118.

⁴⁴ Rakanita Dyah Ayu Kinesti et al., "Pemberian Reward Bagi Siswa Berprestasi Sebagai Strategi Guru Kelas Dalam Pembelajaran Di SD Al-Ma'soem Bandung," *El-Midad: Jurnal Jurusan PGMI* 13, no. 2 (2021): hlm. 104.

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determination to continue to be consistent in learning.⁴⁵ Based on researcher observations, rewards are given when children are independent, active in learning, complete projects on target, have out of the box ideas, and so on. Some reward words given by class A and class B teachers to students such as "you've been great. I'm happy, I love you. I love you, because you are great", "you are great, amazing."

3. PAUD learning assessment is based on the Ministry of Education and Culture No. 56 of 2022. Learning assessment at Aisyiyah BA Cimanggu Kindergarten Cilacap is carried out with five steps, including:

First, establish the research plan and objectives. The assessment assesses all aspects of children's development ranging from religious moral development, cognitive, language, social emotional, physical motor, and art development.⁴⁶ Based on the results of the interview with the Head of Kindergarten, it can be seen that the purpose of the assessment is of course to see the development of learning. Assessments are carried out once a month which is an effort from the school to monitor activities in classroom learning. Growing up as a child and a refugee means navigating a range of hardships and instability while going through significant and quick changes in social-emotional and cognitive development.⁴⁷

Assessment results can be objective and in accordance with existing objectives if the teacher is open in the process. In Permendikbud Number 23 of 2016 in chapter IV Article 5.⁴⁸ The assessment output is a report card or a record of student learning outcomes for one semester. What is recorded in it is the development of students according to their age range.

Second, The supervision assessment technique carried out at Aisyiyah BA Cimanggu Kindergarten Cilacap uses individual supervision techniques in the form of class visits. Based on the results of interviews with the Head of Kindergarten, it can be seen that supervision activities carried out by the Head of Kindergarten are in accordance with standardized assessments by bringing a supervision format, things that are assessed such as teacher readiness in preparing

teaching materials. Furthermore, the kindergarten principal provides suggestions if the teacher still has shortcomings in learning. According to classroom teachers A and B, assessment techniques can be seen from the accuracy in doing projects, tidiness, and activeness. In addition to knowing the development of learning, assessment can also be used as a reporting technique. This is because reporting involves student guardians, so that they become more responsible for their children's development.⁴⁹

Third, implementing the assessment process. Assessment in Aisyiyah BA Cimanggu Kindergarten Cilacap takes place in stages, starting from daily, weekly, monthly, and semesterly assessments. Based on the results of interviews with the head of kindergarten, it can be seen that the learning assessment process can be seen from the lesson plans owned by the teacher and the RPH made every day, so that learning is maximized. Assessment in class A is seen from activeness, while in class B it is done using a photo series.

Fourth, analyze the assessment. Learning assessment should cover all aspects of the learning domain such as cognitive, affective, and psychomotor aspects. To be able to analyze the assessment, teachers can collect all the data obtained during the daily assessment. Based on the results of interviews with class A teachers, it can be seen that assessment analysis is carried out by summarizing all report results. While in class B it can be seen from the assessment analysis can be seen from the results of the best photo series between the first photo, to the last

Fifth, adjusting learning. The intended learning adjustment is learning after the assessment analysis stage, namely reporting the results of activities through report cards. Regarding reporting, Zahro argues that teachers should maintain the confidentiality of data or information about child development.⁵⁰ In general, Aisyiyah institutions have actually implemented an online e-report system from last year called Sipendi. However, due to the teacher's limitations in IT, the class that has just implemented e-report is class B.

⁴⁵ Novan Ardy Wiyani, "Kegiatan Manajerial Dalam Pembudayaann Hidup Bersih Dan Sehat Di Taman Penitipan Anak RA Darussalam Kroya Cilacap," *Jurnal Isema: Islamic Educational* 5, no. 1 (2020): hlm. 22, <https://doi.org/10.15575/isema.v5i1.8180>.

⁴⁶ Delia Nuralita Fajri, Ninik Yulianti, and Luh Putu Indah Budyawati, "Analisis Pelaksanaan Asesmen Perkembangan Anak," *Jurnal Edukasi* 7, no. 2 (2020): hlm. 17-18.

⁴⁷ Ha Yeon Kim et al., "Post-Migration Risks, Developmental Processes, and Learning among Syrian Refugee Children in Lebanon," *Journal of Applied Developmental Psychology* 69 (July 2020): 101142, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.appdev.2020.101142>.

⁴⁸ Ikka Ida Rokhyani, "Penerapan Teknik-Teknik Penilaian Pembelajaran Sejarah Di MAN 1 Yogyakarta" (UNY, 2017).

⁴⁹ Ulya Ainur Rofi'ah and Siti Fatonah, "Asesmen Perkembangan Anak Usia 4-5 Tahun Pada Masa Covid-19," *Yaa Bunayya: Jurnal Pendidikan Anak Usia Dini* 5, no. 2 (2021): hlm. 41.

⁵⁰ Kurnia Mustika Weni, Hasmalena, and Syafricaningsih Syafar, "Analisis Penilaian Pembelajaran Di TK Se-Kecamatan Belitang Oku Timur," *Tumbuh Kembang: Kajian Teori Dan Pembelajaran PAUD* 4, no. 2 (2017): hlm. 7, <https://doi.org/10.36706/jtk.v4i2.8181>.

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CONCLUSIONS

The implementation of the Ministry of Education and Culture No 56 of 2022 at Aisyah BA Cimanggu Kindergarten in Cilacap is considered successful. The reason for the success in implementing learning independence is the strong commitment to implementing the specific objectives made by the school. Through specific objectives, schools understand the needs currently felt by the community. Therefore, all planned learning programs can be implemented well. In accordance with curriculum guidelines, indicators of success can be seen from three steps of PAUD learning, including first, learning planning. In planning, teachers are required to be more creative in choosing learning that suits the characteristics of students; second, the implementation of learning. Learners are also required to be active, independent, collaborative. Evaluation is done through light discussion, activeness, and photo series. Then in the independent curriculum, various project tasks must be done by students in the form of groups. Learners are also required to be active, independent, collaborative; third, learning assessment. In this assessment process, teachers are free to determine the assessment method. Grade A teachers use assessment by observing the results of students' projects in each learning topic, while Grade B teachers prefer to apply photo series as their assessment media.

The limitation of this research is that the curriculum implementation has only been running for one semester. Therefore, given the limitations in the research, the researchers provide several recommendations regarding the independent curriculum that can be researched by other researchers, namely the evaluation of the implementation of the independent curriculum, teacher competency management in the independent curriculum, and supervision management in the independent learning curriculum.

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